

Suggestive Models for Sugar Factories By-product Industries

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Abstract:

India is currently one of the largest producers of cane sugar in the world. Sugarcane is an agro-energy crop and India is the homeland of this crop. It is the second largest agro based industry located in rural areas. It provides direct and indirect employment of millions of farmers, farm workers and factory workers. The sugar industries have primary importance not only from the view point of the utility of the millions of consumers but its importance to large cane growers, manufactures and the Government is equally great.

Introduction:

India is currently one of the largest producers of cane sugar in the world. Sugarcane is an agro-energy crop and India is the homeland of this crop. It is the second largest agro based industry located in rural areas. It provides direct and indirect employment of millions of farmers, farm workers and factory workers. The sugar industries have primary importance not only from the view point of the utility of the millions of consumers but its importance to large cane growers, manufactures and the Government is equally great. Due to their crucial role in the interaction of agricultural sector, industrial sector and consumer, sugar factories are expected to perform both in terms of physical and financial indicators. Any inefficiency on their part would adversely affect of the sugarcane growers, manufactures, consumers and even the Government also.

1. Sugarcane ‘Product Mix’ or ‘By-product Mix’:

To increase the profitability of sugar industries the concept of sugarcane ‘Product Mix’ or ‘By-product Mix’. The sugar factory with several product lines has a product mix. A product mix means consists of all the product lines and items that a particular seller offers for sale. The feature of By-product mix sugar complex are, it is zero waste plant were all by-product generated are further

processed into saleable final product. Bagasse, molasses and press-mud is the primary by-product in sugar factory. The sugar factories are beginning to diversify into multiple by-product to enhance the value addition for every metric ton of cane that is crushed.

2. Suggestive Model for sugar industry:

Some similarity points taken into account for suggestive model all sugar factories in the following:

1. To utilize the full sectioned capacity of sugar factory plant and by-product units.
2. The new marketing strategy of sugar and all by-products need to utilize the modern technique such as forward trading in its local markets, notational markets and international markets. Through this mechanism sugar factory and its byproducts units can make long term contract and sale the sugar and by-products in advance.

Model: I Small capacity sugar factory plant (2000 TCD to 2500 TCD)

1. Distillery of 30 KL.
2. Ethanol plant 30KL Based on Molasses or Sugar cane.
3. Co-generation unit of 15 M.W.
4. Bio-composting Plant.
5. Bio-Gas plant for internal use.

**Model: II Medium Size Sugar factory plant
(3000 TCD to 5000 TCD)**

1. Distillery of 30 KL.
2. Ethanol plant 30 KL Based on Molasses or Sugar cane.
3. Extra Neutral Alcohol plant-30 KL
4. Co-generation plant of 15 M.W. to 20 M.W.
5. Bio-composting Plant.
6. Bio-Gas plant for internal use.

**Model: III Large Scale Sugar factory plant
(7000 TCD to 7500 TCD)**

1. Distillery of 60 KL.
2. Ethanol plant 30 KL Based on Molasses or Sugar cane.
3. Extra Neutral Alcohol plant-30 KL
4. Co-generation plant of 30 M.W. to 45 M.W.
5. Bio-composting Plant With earth worm plant.

Table No.:1 By-products mix models relation to the production, marketing, financial and human resource in the sample sugar factory. (2005-06 to 2012-13) Study Period average figures.

Sr. No.	Particulars	Datta	Kumbhi	Gadingalaj	Warana	Rajaram	Total	Average
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	Total average Capacity sugar factory M.T.	7000	3000	2200	7500	2000	21700	4340
2	Total average sugarcane Crushed in M. T. in lakhs	11.08	5.36	3.23	12.51	3.68	35.86	7.172
3	Total average sugar produced in quintals in lakhs	13.85	6.96	3.93	15.9	4.44	45.08	9.01
4	Average Bagase produced in M.T. in lakhs	3.19	1.56	0.95	3.6	1.03	10.33	2.06
	Average Bagase available to sales in M.T.	26062	13414	7001	87297	13693	147467	29493.40
	Average bagase sales in M.T	19300	10683	3380	65413	13393	112169	22433.80
	Average bagase sales in price in lackh Rs.	169.31	106.62	33.05	704.3	156.07	1169.35	233.87
5	Average Molasses produced in thousand M.T.	42	18.65	12.12	42.22	15	129.99	25.99
	Average Molasses sales in thousand M.T	39.96	17.67	12.23	41.8	15.07	126.73	25.34
	Average Molasses sales in price in lackh Rs.	1517.66	562.51	325.68	1960.83	583.56	4950.24	990.04
6	Average Compost produced in thousand M.T.	37.17	21.74	7.95	23.39	0	90.25	18.05
	Average Compost sales in thousand M.T	35.59	20.99	6.27	23.86	0	86.71	17.34
	Average Compost sales in price in lackh Rs.	70.87	27.06	14.92	68.21	0	181.06	36.21
7	Total average Capacity Distillery plant.	60000	30000	25000	60000	N.A.	175000	43750
8	Average rectified sprit produce in lakh lit.	100.15	42.34	38.16	107	N.A.	287.65	71.91
	Average rectified sprit sales in lakh lit.	68.4	10.12	4.67	52.19	N.A.	135.38	33.84
	Average rectified sprit closing balance in lakh lit.	16.2	12.03	14.4	25.99	N.A.	68.62	17.15
	Average rectified sprit sales price in lakh Rs.	1765.21	243.09	113.11	1520.03	N.A.	3641.44	910.36
9	Average SDS sprit produce in lakh lit.	18.59	33.44	30.34	15.63	N.A.	98	24.50
	Average SDS sprit sales in lakh lit.	19.01	32.06	30.24	15.18	N.A.	96.18	24.12
	Average SDS sprit sales price in lakh Rs..	355.54	722.11	651.96	357.23	N.A.	2086.84	521.71
10	Average ODS sprit produce in lakh lit.	0.49	0.7	0	0	N.A.	1.19	0.29

	Average ODS sprit sales in lakh lit.	0.48	0.69	0	0	N.A.	1.17	0.29
	Average ODS sprit sales price in lakh Rs..	11.52	14.55	0	0	N.A.	26.07	6.51
11	Average Fusil oil produce in lakh lit.	0.24	0.01	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	0.25	0.06
	Average fusil oilt sales in lakh lit.	0.23	0	0	0	N.A.	0.23	0.05
	Average Fusil oil sales price in lakh Rs..	4.79	0	0	0	N.A.	4.79	1.19
12	Total average Capacity Ethanol plant.	30000	N.A.	N.A.	30000	N.A.	60000	30000
	Average ethanol produce in lakh lit.	9.24	N.A.	N.A.	9.78	N.A.	19.02	9.51
	Average ethanol sales in lakh lit.	9.81	N.A.	N.A.	10.97	N.A.	20.78	10.39
	Average ethanol closing balance in lakh lit.	0.88	N.A.	N.A.	1.78	N.A.	2.66	1.33
	Average ethanol sales price in lakh Rs..	255.49	N.A.	N.A.	225.06	N.A.	480.55	240.27
13	Total average Capacity ENA plant.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	55000	N.A.	55000	55000
	Average ENA produce in lakh lit.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	20.12	N.A.	20.12	20.12
	Average ENA sales in lakh lit.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	19.91	N.A.	19.91	19.91
	Average ENA closing balance in lakh lit.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	0	N.A.	0	0
	Average ENA sales price in lakh Rs..	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	592.99	N.A.	592.99	592.99
14	Total average Capacity pulp plant 20 TCD (Yearly-6000M.T.)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	20	N.A.	20	20
	Average Pulp produced in M.T.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	775	N.A.	775	775
	Average Pulp sales in M.T	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	762	N.A.	762	762
	Average Pulp sales in price in lakh Rs.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	133.21	N.A.	133.21	133.21
15	Total average Capacity lignosulphonate plant 8 TCD (Yearly-2400M.T.)	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	8	N.A.	8	8
	Average lignosulphonate produced in M.T.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	1039	N.A.	1039	1039
	Average lignosulphonate sales in M.T	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	950	N.A.	950	950
	Average lignosulphonate sales in price in lakh Rs.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	60.24	N.A.	60.24	60.24
16	Average Manpower utilization in by-product department	77	77	51	142	N.A.	347	86.75
17	Finalcial position in sugar factory relation to by product department							
	Net Sugar Income in lack in lakh Rs Rs.	29298.08	14968.83	8267.67	45151.87	9753.15	107439.6	21487.92
	Net By Product Income in lakh Rs (Bagasse, molasses, Press Mud)	2153.78	783.06	382.2	3058.83	740.01	7117.88	1423.57
	Other Income in lackh Rs	987.12	169.92	110.74	2075.53	85.92	3429.23	685.84
	Affiliated Business income	0	0	0	829.94	0	829.94	165.98
	Distillery Profit in lackh Rs	451.16	270.22	154.82	396.56	0	1272.76	254.55
	Paper Mill Profit	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
18	Average Total Income	32890.14	16192.03	8915.43	51512.73	10579.08	120089.4	4002.98
19	Average Cost of production Distillery, Ethanol,and ENA per litre in Rs.	20.11	13	15.72	18.97	N.A.	67.8	16.95

20	Average Cost of production pulp and lignosulfonate per M.T.	N.A	N.A	N.A	34822.4	N.A.	34822.4	34822.39
21	Average loss pulp and lignosulfonate	N.A	N.A	N.A	-215.15	N.A.	-215.15	-215.148
22	Total average cost of production distillery, ethanol and ENA in Rs. In lakh.	1956.93	560.31	489.72	2140.79	N.A.	5147.75	1286.93
23	Total investment in fixed assets sugar factory in lakh Rs	5065.06	5793.43	3288.12	22100.58	2785.83	39033.02	7806.66
24	Total investment in fixed assets Distillery in lakh Rs	1158.8	1439.89	1310.44	4147.6	N.A	8056.73	2014.18
25	Total investment in fixed assets Ethanol in lakh Rs	140.12	N.A	N.A	106.82	246.94	246.82	123.47
26	Total investment in fixed assets paper mill in lakh Rs	N.A	N.A	N.A	1027.29	N.A	1027.29	1027.29

Source: Field work

Note:- N.A. - Not applicable i.e. These sugar factories have not producing.

Conclusion:

Sugar industry is cyclic and is susceptible to the vagaries of nature. Moreover it is subject to various controls which restrict its profitability. These factors make it necessary to develop the concept of sugar mill By-product Mix Model which should consist of in addition to sugar i.e. distillery plant, ethanol plant, Extra Neutral Alcohol Plant, Co-generation plant all these plant to supplement the profitability of parent unit and take care of any fluctuation in the operation of sugar factory. The table no.1, Sr. no.17 shows financial position in sugar factory and relation to by-product department. An average net sugar income in lakh is Datta-Rs.29298.08, Kumbhi-Rs.14968.83, Gadingalaj-Rs.8267.67, Warana- Rs.45151.87 and Rajaram-Rs.9753.15 in the study period and average all sample unit is Rs. 21487.92 lakh. Average net by-product income in lakh are Datta-Rs.2153.78, Kumbhi-Rs.783.06, Gadingalaj-Rs.382.2, Warana-Rs.3058.83 and Rajaram-Rs.740.01 in the study period and average all sample unit is Rs.1423.57 lakh. Average net average distillery profit in lakh are Datta-Rs.451.16, Kumbhi-Rs.270.22, Gadingalaj-Rs.154.82 and Warana- Rs.396.56 in the

study period and average all sample unit is Rs.254.55 lakh.

Because of this calculation with capacity utilization to distillery profit is found Kumbhi highest capacity utilization in its small plant and lowest total capacity utilization is found in Warana. For better financial and economical performance Datta distilleries and its ethanol plant and Warana distilleries and its ethanol and ENA plants should efficiently use their capacity utilization. And also it will reduce cost of production and increase income from distilleries by-products.

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